

MODERN MEDICINE VERSUS TRADITIONAL MEDICINE AND NATURAL
MEDICINE AND NATURAL TREATMENT.

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Annotation: In this essay I explore that how medicine came to this advancement as well as Modern medicine is the use of scientifically approved therapeutic systems and diagnostic methodology to treat illnesses

Key words: modern advances, diagnosing, medical improvement, Ancient Greece, resulting in operations, injured individuals, the effectiveness of the specialization of knowledge.

Few would contest that advancements in modern medicine have improved the lives of people today. The development of antibiotics, vaccines, cancer treatments, and more means that people are living longer and healthier lives than at any point in the past. Modern advances in medicine, as in other areas, originate in Ancient Times. Today, people are accustomed to the availability and safety of the process of diagnosing and treating various diseases. However, it took humanity many centuries and millennia to achieve this level of medicine. According to numerous studies, there is an assumption that “medicine began to originate in Ancient Greece” (Harust et al. 18). However, various types of healing practices existed in all corners of the Ancient World. The development of science and technology went side by side with the spread of medicine, which made it far from perfect and sometimes even dangerous. In some Asian and African countries, up to 80% of the population relies on traditional medicine for their primary health care needs. Traditional medicine is a form of alternative medicine. Practices known as traditional medicines include traditional European medicine, traditional Chinese medicine, traditional Korean medicine.

In the developed world, evidence-based medicine is not universally used in clinical practice; for example, a 2007 survey of literature reviews found that about 49% of the interventions lacked sufficient evidence to support either benefit or harm. Modern Medicine was built around the model of running tests on sick patients to determine which drug or medical procedure would best deal with some illness. This makes Modern Medicine more precise in determining the diagnosis and how to treat this specific disease. This means it saves time whether in treatment or recovery and resources. In the meantime Traditional Medicine practices based on the theories, beliefs, and experiences that passed on hereditarily, the prognosis is slightly off. Since it's not targeting on a specific treatment, especially if the patient consumes herbal medicine where the sustention is not only the proper agent that needed. This will take more time to show the effect if the treatment works or not.

Medical improvements allowed doctors to expand their knowledge from World War I to modern medicine by changing the way medical care is executed in order to aid in the care of injured individuals. The advancement of medicine in the United States was seen in discovery of vaccines that led to the control of diseases that impact civilians in the United States today. As a result, developments in surgeries taken in various medical specialties and treatments resulting in operations used today. Overall, medicine of World War One era had a significant impact on

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modern healthcare. Medicine these days has changed a lot because of advances in technology. Medicine in the past was dependent on man knowledge and experience not in specialized knowledge as with new medicine. New medicine depends on the study of biology and cell life history. There is a similarity between medicine now and in the past e.g. The principle, the concept and the belief. They are different in the way of diagnoses, medical equipment, medication and the way of treatment.

Traditional medicine comprises medical aspects of traditional knowledge that developed over generations within the folk beliefs of various societies, including indigenous peoples, before the era of modern medicine. On the other hand, Modern Medicine considered more effective since the approach and method they use are more specific in diagnosing diseases and how to treat them. Modern medicine is also scientifically proved. Modern medicine views disease only as a biological condition characterized by abnormalities in the function or structure of certain organs or entire organ systems. While alternative medicine or traditional medicine considers disease more than meets the eyes, besides being biological, they also involve certain aspects like spiritual, psychological, and certain social of the affected person. This is something that modern medicine often ignores.

The conclusion is that even as effective as modern medicine can get, there's some aspect that Modern Medicine ignores, which some of this aspect can be crucial to the success of the treatment or the wellness of the patient. here's when the traditional medicine steps in to fill the blank. as who stated through strict rules and regulations that Traditional and Complementary Medicine can be used to accompany or as a secondary option to modern medicine. It's not to determine which one is better than the other, each has advantages and disadvantages of its own. But it's to complement each other to achieve the same goal, well being of mankind.

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